

**The North American Cosmological Model:
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Cosmology is not how humans measure in time. But what the universe does in space. Welcome to The North American Cosmological model.

When I was child. Just like you I too sat in the back seat. I also looked out the window. I asked, "why don't the stars not move. The car is moving, "why aren't the stars". To help understand this. Is the first aspect I wanted to explain. Is that, centuries ago; Astronomers had to use the standard tools of their time. Most used rocks, higher elevation. Some went to the shores of their geographical region. In fact many used the bow of ships. Sailors would use the stars to navigate. These stars are "still" in our sky.

When I undertook the idea of creating The North America Cosmological model. I had to learn about key topics to understand how to present this new Cosmological model. For centuries, the idea of "light" photons/ stellar radiation. Was bound to the idea of a "clock". Now this may seem pointless. But, it's not. In fact light has given us the one aspect that can unify the universe. You're probably thinking. "Sure" they did that years ago in 1993. You're right. "they" did. It's the Λ CDM model, or lambda cold dark matter model.

Now that you know what we are discussing. Let me enlighten you on the "how". For decades we have been taught that the 4th dimension of "spacetime" is the cosmological constant. This is not the case. It's a constant for a "photon". "Not" the human observer. You're probably asking, "human observer" ?

Allow me to explain. For nearly the past 70 years. The standard model of cosmology "removes" the human observer for mathematics and biases. The North American Cosmological Model, "returns" the human observer back into the studies and observations.

"How" ? You might ask. "Well", this is how.

For the past 20 years of my life. I have taken upon myself to actively study the science involving: "cosmology", "physics", and "quantum mechanics" (waveform) analysis through "asterosismology". These studies involve: "pressure" how much force is applied. "Gravitation" is the decay of motion applied to mass; and "distance" is how much space is between "you" the observer and the object you're observing.

Let's start at the beginning. In the past summer of July of 2025. I had posed a question. "Why do galaxies spin opposite from one another. As seen in the Coriolis effect we observe on earth".

What possible explanation could there be. The standard model would invoke dark matter distribution here. Dark energetic anomalous there.

I had a very hard time trying to find a way to explain the actions using the standard model placeholders. I had to go back to basics.

Gravity:

Gravity: "is the decay of motion applied to mass. Stabilized by the angular momentum trajectory of the host center of mass".

Sir' Isaac Newton had a great start at this. We know the story. How the apple fell from the tree. That story. Now let me explain how and what is happening to the apple, and your eyes as you watch it fall..

When I was in gym class, my physical education teacher had us jump on a trampoline. Best time spent as a child. However, let's talk about what is going on here. As you jump up from the trampoline. The elastic rubber fabric bends as you apply weight/ force. Then that force meets a pressure threshold. You then are gravitationally displaced upwards. This is the "bounce" we experience as children.

Now how does "Newton" come in? Well, it's simple. He gave us the idea of how gravity acts. This is simply explaining. "What" is making that act take place. For instance: you in this case would be the apple falling. Now the standard model would have you believe that "gravity" is the fiber sheet of the trampoline. See, "how" offset this is. Let's undo this. You, the "observer" is the apple. Now since you know you are going to fall to earth. The bounce, then you falling down on the trampoline. Gravity is the reason you fall. Your mass alone against the mass of earth is dwarfed.

Your small human mass simply has no chance of avoiding stabilization. That's why we stand up and walk upright against the ground. Earth's surface.

Okay. I know what you're probably thinking, "sure" but about at a distance. Okay. Let's begin with what, (the earth). Its mass is large. It orbits another large mass.

In this gravitational relationship. We can place instruments at certain areas of observation outside of earth. Take the JWST. This observatory/ telescope sits at one such place. Now, I was talking about gravity at a distance. Here we go..

When you sit on a til-a-whirl. You're anchored in the carnival ride. Then it starts to rotate. You begin to feel a "tug" left and right. This is because you're moving against the earth's rotation. Your carriage is being spun faster than your own mass can accelerate on its own. Thus, you feel that "dizzy" euphoric feeling of the adrenaline of the carnival ride.

Our galaxy is a lot like that ride. A more apt analogy would be: "hippo on a turntable".

Okay, okay I know.. this was a lot to take in. Let me clear the fog. "You", the observer like myself. Have instincts. These allow us to interpret our environment. When it's dark, we shine a luminous light to guide or make a dark space bright.

In cosmology. The North American Cosmological Model. Is showing us that luminosity. The "massless" photons that are in nearly every direction we look out into the sky. The bright twinkles, the massive orange and yellow balls of gas. Even the more recent large red ones. These stars predate humans. Let that sink in for "one" moment. "**All**" stars in the night sky predate humans.

So remember my childhood memory; That took place nearly twenty years ago. Those same stars have existed for every human observer to witness. That logic led to navigation, GPS, technology as we know it today. It all stems from what humans did centuries ago. Looked out at the stars and asked, "how" do we exist inside this universe.

That is in the next paper(s). All of which are located here in the same archive. The framework is called: "Quantum Gravity Model Framework". The framework helps the observer understand the predictive nature of: The North American Cosmological Model.